

Photochemical and Thermal Transformations of O-Alkyl-S-phthalylalanyl Xanthates

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Manuscript received 21 April 1986, revised 17 December 1987, accepted 22 December 1987

The reaction of phthalylalanyl chloride with different potassium O-alkylxanthates (R=Et, n-pr, iso-pr, n-Bu, iso-Bu) around 0° in ether solution gave rise to the corresponding O-alkyl-S-phthalylalanyl xanthates. Irradiation of the latter in benzene solution gave xanthic acid disulphide, phthalylalanine and thioanhydride of phthalylalanine in addition to some other products. Thermal decomposition of these acylxanthates around 150–60° for 15–20 min yielded the corresponding esters and carbon disulphide.

THE photochemical and thermal transformations of O-alkyl-S-phthalylglycyl xanthates studied by the authors¹ revealed that the mode of fragmentation was similar to that suggested by earlier workers^{2,3}. Photolysis of phthalimide system with a sulphur atom in N-alkyl side chain has been reported⁴ to undergo intramolecular hydrogen abstraction. We have studied the photochemical and thermal transformations of an extended side chain xanthate such as O-alkyl-S-phthalylalanyl xanthates.

Treatment of an ether-solution of phthalylalanyl chloride (1) with potassium O-alkylxanthates around 0° gave phthalylalanyl xanthates (2a–e) in good yields (Table 1). The structure of the xanthates (2a–e) have been elucidated on the basis of analytical and spectral data. The ir spectra of 2c showed absorption bands at 1720, 1385, 1370 (doublet) and 1260 cm⁻¹ due to the presence of imide, isopropyl and thiocarbonyl groups, respectively. The uv spectra of 2c showed absorption maximum at 395 nm, characteristic of aroyl xanthates^{2,5}. The pmr spectra of 2c displayed signals at δ 7.7 (4H, m, ArH), 4.0 (2H, t, NCH₂), 3.1 (2H, t, CH₂CO), 1.5 (6H, d, (CH₃)₂C) and 5.7 (1H, m, CH).

In a representative run, an acetone solution of phthalylalanyl chloride (1) treated with potassium O-ethylxanthate around 0° gave thioanhydride of phthalylalanine (3) (Scheme 1). A similar observation has been made in the attempted preparation of a few other acylxanthates^{2,3,6}.

Photolysis of the xanthates 2a–e in benzene solution resulted in the formation of various products which included xanthic acid disulphide (8), phthalylalanine (9) and thioanhydride of phthalylalanine (3). A probable mechanism which explains the formation of these products involves the initial fragmentation of either CO–S or CS–S bond^{5,7}. The fission of CO–S bond gave initially acyl radical (5) and xanthate radical (4). Another mode of fission resulted in radicals 6 and 7. The radical 6 can

Scheme 1

combine with the radical 5 to give thioanhydride 3 (Scheme 2). The dimerisation of xanthate radical

Scheme 2

4 gave xanthic acid disulphide (8). The formation of phthalylalanine (9) can be explained through the formation of the corresponding aldehyde⁷. The dimeric products of radicals 5 and 7 were not observed in the photolysis of these xanthates (2a-e).

Thermal decomposition of acyl xanthates are reported to give esters and carbon disulphide⁸. For example, when phthalylalanyl xanthates (2) were heated around 150–60° for 15–20 min, the corresponding esters 10 and carbon disulphide were formed (Scheme 3). The structure of the esters (10) were confirmed by m.m.p. and analytical data (Table 1). A four-membered transition state has been suggested for such decomposition^{8,9}. However, thermal decomposition of 2c resulted in the formation of thioanhydride 3 and the corresponding ester was not formed. A similar observation was made by Singh and George⁹ in the thermal decomposition of *O*-ethyl-*S*-triphenyl acetyl xanthate. A probable mechanism for the formation of 3 in thermal decomposition of the xanthate 2c is shown in Scheme 3.

Experimental

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and uv spectra on a Specord UV-VIS spectrophotometer, and nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer. Irradiations were carried out in a Hanovia photochemical reaction assembly with a quartz immersion well and high pressure mercury lamp.

O-Alkyl-*S*-phthalylalanyl xanthates (2a-e): To a solution of 1⁹ (0.01 mol) in ether (150 ml) was added potassium *O*-alkylxanthate¹⁰ (0.01 mol) portionwise with constant stirring at 0° for 30 min. The precipitated KCl was filtered and ether solution of the xanthate was washed with aqueous 1% NaHCO₃. The ether extract was washed repeatedly with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed in vacuum to give the xanthates 2a-e which were recrystallised from a mixture (1:1) of ether-petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). The analytical and physical data of 2a-e are shown in Table 1.

Thioanhydride of phthalylalanine (3): To a solution of 1 (4.8 g, 0.02 mol) in acetone (100 ml) was added potassium *O*-ethylxanthate (3.2 g, 0.02 mol) portionwise with constant stirring at 0° for

30 min. The precipitated KCl was filtered off and the removal of solvent in vacuum afforded 3, after recrystallisation from benzene (Table 1), $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 1750 and 1700 cm⁻¹ (CO-S-CO); δ 7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 3.8 (4H, t, N-CH₂) and 2.9 (4H, t, CH₂CO).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF *O*-ALKYL-*S*-PHTHALYLALANYL XANTHATES (2), THIOANHYDRIDE OF PHTHALYLALANINE (3) AND THE ESTERS (10)^a

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	60–1	75
2b	78–9	53
2c	79–81	58
2d	58–9	53
2e	63–4	44
3	197–200	38
10a	74–5	46
10b	66–8	65
10d	63–5	58
10e	60–2	55

^aC and H analyses found satisfactory.

Photolysis of O-alkyl-S-phthalylalanyl xanthates (2a-e): A solution of 2a-e (1 g) in dry benzene (450 ml, AnalaR) was irradiated for 1 h with a high pressure mercury lamp (250 W). The removal of solvent gave a gummy solid which was extracted in petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). The removal of solvent gave xanthic acid disulphides (8) which were compared on tlc with authentic samples¹¹.

The insoluble residue was extracted in chloroform and washed with aqueous 1% NaHCO₃. The aqueous layer on acidification with dilute HCl (1:1) gave phthalylalanine 9, m.p. 150° (m.m.p.). The chloroform layer was repeatedly washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed in vacuum to give thioanhydride 3, m.p. 197°–200°.

Thermal decomposition of O-alkyl-S-phthalylalanyl xanthates (2a-e): The xanthates (2; 1 g) were heated under nitrogen atmosphere in an oil-bath at 150–60° for 15–20 min. The gaseous product was trapped by passing through piperidine solution (5 ml in 50 ml ether) which gave piperidinium cyclopentamethylenedithiocarbamate, m.p. 169° (lit.⁵ 169°). The residual mass, on recrystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) gave the esters of phthalylalanine 10 (Table 1).

However, thermal decomposition of 2c (1 g) in the usual procedure gave thioanhydride 3 (0.50 g, 77%), m.p. 197°–200° and not the expected ester.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. P. K. Bhattacharya, for facilities and to Dr. S. S. Lele and Mr. S. S. Madhavarao for analytical data.

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